

Scalable and Quantum Resilient Heterogeneous Edge Computing enabling Trustworthy AI (SMARTY)

J.J. Vegas Olmos
NVIDIA Corporation
Yokneam, Israel
Email: juanj@nvidia.com

Filippo Cugini
CNIT
Pisa, Italy
Email: filippo.cugini@cnit.it

Pedro Reviriego
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
Email: pedro.reviriego@upm.es

Abstract—The emergence of AI as a pervasive technology that is pushed to the edge poses several challenges as heterogeneous devices, networks, and systems are loosely controlled and potentially more vulnerable to attackers. Ensuring that Edge AI is trustworthy is a key design requirement that poses several research challenges. This paper first provides an overview of the main challenges that have to be addressed in Edge AI and then presents the vision and planned work in SMARTY, a project funded by the European Union Chips Joint Undertaking, that is designed to address those challenges in a comprehensive manner providing end-to-end trustworthy solutions that include hardware, software, and network technologies.

Index Terms—Edge AI, trustworthy, confidential computing, networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Trustworthy artificial intelligence (AI) is a critical concern when it comes to edge computing. Edge computing involves processing data at the edge of the network, close to where the data is generated, rather than sending it to a centralized location [1]. This approach can provide faster and more efficient data processing, but it also requires that AI systems operate autonomously and reliably in remote environments. Therefore, it is important that AI systems in edge computing are trustworthy, meaning they are transparent, secure, and accurate [2]. In more detail, ideally, trustworthy AI can be deployed transparently from any point in the network, securely and accurately. Fundamentally, these requirements translate into offering protection of data-in-transit and data-in-process, while ensuring low latency and accessibility. In the following, we describe how those technological challenges can be tackled.

- **Data-in-Transit:** protecting data-in-transit can be done through post-quantum cryptography (PQC), the only methodology that protects data against classic processors and quantum computers being used to break down communication channels [3]. Post-quantum cryptography is important because it addresses the threat posed by quantum computers to current cryptographic systems. Quantum computers are expected to be able to break many of the encryption schemes that are currently used to secure sensitive data, including financial transactions, medical

records, and government communications. Post-quantum cryptography aims to develop new cryptographic systems that are resistant to quantum computer attacks, ensuring that sensitive information remains secure even in the face of quantum computing advancements. This has to be done at a reasonable complexity and with efficient implementations that can run on real-time in edge devices.

- **Data-in-Process:** protection of data-in-process can be achieved through the adoption of confidential computing and software-defined perimeters (SDP), protecting individual processing units or clusters of units from hardware to software [4]. Data is processed in secured and trusted environments, even in the presence of potentially malicious actors, in enclaves that are isolated at both hardware and software levels. Since workloads are dynamic, these enclaves change dynamically, not only in resources but also in security levels. Those enclaves are defined and loaded through orchestration systems that can adapt to different security level requests and various AI loads.
- **Transparency and accuracy:** Transparency relates to the ability of creating end-to-end AI architectures that integrate AI-based algorithms and devices to support interoperability, upgradability, and trusted exchangeability. These features can be achieved through standardized APIs across resource-constrained device-connected systems, including interfaces between sensing/actuation and computation, edge processing units, on-premises servers, and other critical components. Devices will be capable of learning at the edge, evolving their AI/ML models incrementally over time (with support for transfer learning and meta-learning), coordinating with one another as a swarm, combining their updates, and communicating the results (including potential cognitive reasoning tasks) in a meaningful way. The goal is to integrate smart edge devices that operate with a high degree of autonomy addressing trustworthiness and sovereignty, while providing scalability, energy efficiency, low latency and robustness.

This paper first discusses the main challenges to making trustworthy AI a reality and then presents the SMARTY

project that aims to address those challenges with several research activities over the next three years. The research challenges are summarized in section II and SMARTY planned research activities and methodology in section III. The paper ends with the conclusions in section IV

II. TRUSTWORTHY EDGE AI RESEARCH CHALLENGES

Ideally, Edge AI would provide secure and trustworthy dynamic integration of decentralized intelligence within the cloud-edge continuum, while ensuring reliability, privacy, and scalability at runtime. To achieve these objectives, there is a need for secure and auditable interactions between the involved devices, making sure that all system interactions are trustworthy and transparent. Innovative secure communication paradigms and encryption algorithms to guarantee secure data transmission and storage are also needed. The seamless and online discoverability and composability of autonomous edge intelligence can be achieved through the use of a semantic-based interplay strategy that facilitates the interaction between the edge devices of such systems, enabling secure, trustworthy, and auditable usage of edge intelligence. These objectives pose significant challenges that can be addressed through the development of novel technologies in four technology areas, described in the following subsections.

A. Quantum resilience hardware and software

In-line encryption using Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) – the gold standard in encryption – is ubiquitously incorporated in data-communications and telecommunications systems as a mean of protection against malignant third parties. The encryption premise is simple: by encrypting using 256 bits keys, the complexity to decrypting using brute force is high enough to prevent any real breaching. However, the rapid development of quantum computing constitutes a significant threat to modern public-key cryptography (PKC) systems. As quantum computers continue to find their way to mass-markets, we are about to witness a challenging situation: the use of Shor’s algorithm with potential powerful quantum computers could easily break most widely used public key cryptosystems (i.e. Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) and Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC), based on integer factorization and discrete logarithm problems. For this, post-quantum cryptography (PQC) based on alternative mathematical features has become a fundamental research topic due to its resistance against quantum computers [3]. Years of fundamental research in the area of mathematics has led to a solid body of work showing that PQC systems based on hash-based cryptography, lattice-based cryptography, code-based cryptography, and multivariate-quadratic cryptography are extremely difficult to break with large quantum computers. The current challenge is twofold: a) how to transport this body of work to the engineering area, where practical use cases can be implemented using these methodologies, b) how to implement those methodologies into hardware operating at line rate, rather than being used through off-line processing [5]. Therefore, strong research and development (R&D) is required in both

hardware systems and software algorithms, but also in network integration, as those systems need to be operating within the context of networks.

B. Confidential Computing and Software Defined Perimeters

Data traversing the Ether or the network can be protected against quantum threads as described in the previous objective through PQC. Once data traverses the network and reaches processing platforms (cloud or edge computing platforms), its integrity is currently not ensured. Confidential Computing protects data in use by isolating it in protected processing enclaves during processing [6]. Confidential computing enables hardware-based Trusted Execution Environment (TEE). These secure and isolated environments prevent unauthorized access or modification of applications and data while in use, thereby increasing the security assurances for organizations that manage sensitive and regulated data. Hence, Confidential Computing is the enabling technology to effectively implement Zero-Trust system, which seeks to (i) authenticate and authorize access to data and (ii) encrypt data in transit, in rest and in processing. The current challenge is twofold: a) how to accelerate the adoption of Trusted Execution Environments to enable Confidential Computing and implement zero-trust policies, where practical use cases can be implemented using these methodologies, b) how to implement those methodologies into hardware operating at line-rate, rather than being used through off-line processing, and in coordination with other cybersecurity measures. Therefore, strong research and development (R&D) is required in both hardware systems and software algorithms, but also in network integration, as those systems need to be operating within the context of networks.

Software-defined perimeters (SDPs) and confidential computing are both related to improving the security of cloud computing environments. SDPs are a security architecture that creates a secure, isolated network connection between the user and the application. This connection is dynamically established using cryptographic techniques, and access to the application is granted only to authorized users. Confidential computing, on the other hand, is a set of technologies and practices that protect data in use, ensuring that sensitive data is never exposed, even to the cloud provider. Confidential computing technologies use hardware-based encryption to isolate and protect data in memory and prevent unauthorized access. SDPs and confidential computing can be used together to enhance the security of cloud computing environments. SDPs can provide an additional layer of security by ensuring that only authorized users can access the application, while confidential computing can protect the data that is being processed within the application. Together, these technologies can help mitigate the risks associated with data breaches and other cyber-attacks.

C. AI-oriented programmable Data Plane Frameworks

PQC and CC need to be complemented with networking technologies that are able to (re)-program communication pipelines, in order to enable “Software Defined” type of

underlying communication fabrics. For this purpose, novel AI-oriented programmable data plane frameworks with optimal Decentralized Feature Extraction (DFE) for security Federated Learning and Wire speed AI (WAI) functionality for security mitigation functions at the data plane are needed. Those can be built using programmable 6G infrastructure resources, including SDN bare metal switches, smart NICs, DPUs, O-RAN and RIC, edge/IoT containers, and eBPF. Embedded Federated Learning nodes in infrastructure elements, can use DFE to extract stateless and stateful traffic features for learning nodes. Edge computing also plays a central role as a supporting paradigm to enable novel solutions that directly improve the performance of factory floors. Edge computing, in its processing aspect, relies on locally placed processing units. Computing processing units (CPUs) are extremely flexible, but their general-purpose limits the agility to work with AI processes. Graphic processing units (GPU) are the processor of choice for deep learning processes because of their native ability to manage large matrixes. Deep neural networks (DNN) processing units can be separated in two blocks: soft deep processing units (DPU) and hard DPUs. Soft DPUs are in essence FPGAs, which can be reprogrammed by the user depending on the AI process. Hard DPU are reconfigurable blocks intended for specific AI functions, such as Google TPUs and Movidius processing units; Hard DPUs are reconfigurable, but only to a limited extend. Finally, full application-specific integrated circuit (ASICs) are specific oriented cores, very efficient but without the opportunity to re-utilization for different processes that those initially intended for.

D. Semantic and Low-code Programmability

Middleware and tools for continuous semantic integration are needed to interact with complex heterogeneous components and systems according to a (i) standardized semantic interface, via a (ii) continuous conversion process based on declarative mappings and scalable from edge to cloud, and (iii) providing a declarative approach for the creation and orchestration of apps based on swarm intelligence. Semantic integration allows for reduced complexity and configuration time swarm intelligence Apps through the automatic instantiation and orchestration of template-based specifications that will deploy AI workloads seamlessly. Dynamic Swarm Networking becomes a key element as it provides a federated fabric for trust-worthy AI and works in combination with underlying Software Defined Perimeters. Dynamic Swarm Networking potentially offers (i) automatic discovery and dynamic network swarm formation in near real time, (ii) hardware-accelerated in-network operations for context-aware swarm networking, and (iii) embedded network security. There are other techniques that can be used to address this challenge such as low-code Programming Tools for Edge Intelligence providing (i) semantic-driven multimodal stream fusion for Edge devices; (ii) swarm elasticity via Edge-Cloud Interplay; (iii) adaptive coordination and optimization; (iv) cross-layer toolchain for Device-Edge-Cloud Continuum.

III. THE SMARTY PROJECT: ARCHITECTURE AND VISION

Figure 1 shows the edge-cloud continuum envisioned in SMARTY: deep edge nodes are operating under limited connectivity and low power conditions. Those can be mobile devices supporting fintech applications, autonomous robots in factory environments, or connected cars. However, this does not preclude local processing power for AI processes and establishment of quantum resilient links. These deep edge nodes contain both communication accelerators as well as processing units upgradeable through PQC-based processes. Since the processing capabilities of those deep edge nodes are low, they can access edge computing platforms. The edge computing platform may be highly dense edge micro data centers or lite edge nodes; regardless of the entrance point, processes can be offloaded through light containers. In addition, cloud fabrics can be connected to the edge platform. All these links are based on PQC principles, creating a quantum resilience for data-in-transfer. At the edge platform, processing blocks operate under confidential computing principles, in which trust is secured at both HW/SW level. In addition, software defined perimeters (SDP) can be created to cluster CC-based processors. This ecosystem is accessed by services/applications, which in SMARTY are driven by different use cases. SMARTY hence proposes a migration from a quantum unsafe processors and communication channels towards a quantum resilience environment, protecting data-in-transit and in-process, and hence allowing for the deployment of critical AI processes with high level of trust requirements. In general, AI systems requiring real-time (few milliseconds) or near-real-time processing (seconds) can only be deployed on networks with high level of trust in the infrastructure supporting it.

A. Heterogeneous Fabrics

A key subject in SMARTY is how to deal with the heterogeneous fabric or infrastructure; the proposed SMARTY solution is based on a semantic data model-driven, cross-layer low-code toolchain, as illustrated in Figure 2. The toolchain includes a semantic-based middleware toolset (known as DataOps) that can be dynamically composed by smart applications. The middleware is designed to be embedded in resource-constrained devices, which allows as many of its components to be utilized as possible. In this context, each application is built on top of the dynamic and distributed services provided by the autonomous edge devices that act as constituent components. Even as the individual components comprising the application change, the application persists. The middleware deployed on the network edge devices of swarm intelligence can operate using a human and machine-readable semantic-driven data model. This functionality promotes the autonomous discovery and interplay of edge devices at the semantic level. The applications are defined as dynamic, hierarchical, and distributed graphs of swarm elements, such as components, services, devices, computing platforms (cloud), communication paths between components, authority/ownership relations, and usage and coordination relationships.

Fig. 1. Edge-cloud continuum in SMARTY supporting trustworthy-needed AI processes.

Fig. 2. SMARTY migration path: today and tomorrow.

A Smart-X application (a generic application based on AI and relying on high level of trust) can be programmed via the dynamic integration of heterogeneous sensing capabilities with different sensing, actuating and computing capabilities. Such integration is specified as a particular graph structure that selects specific sub-group of nodes, based on a semantic-based criteria, e.g., “select traffic events at nearby junctions”. The semantic-based criteria require the middleware to be able to reason on attributes of participant nodes by their “meaning”. e.g., “traffic events”, “nearby”, which are formally represented as ontological concepts and properties. Such criteria are represented in standardized semantic representations, e.g., sensor fusion queries as the input for multimodal sensor fusion to compose constituent AI models at runtime. The runtime is not only composed of DataOps, NetOps and AI models but also coordination and optimization tools to enable a seamless interplay of device-edge-continuum. To this end, the application builder can federate an application logic to distributed edges to autonomously coordinate and monitor control loops, using the collective intelligence of the member edges. A network edge, e.g., an edge gateway, a cloud computing service or an intermediate routing device, exposes its internal functions to

other edge devices via a self-described system model using Standardized Semantic Data models (SSDM). The SSDM-based system model is driven by taxonomies/ontologies as the common understanding among domain experts, developers and machines. With the interoperability at semantic level, this intelligent software can dynamically form a coalition to create a distributed processing flow across swarm intelligence without having to agree about the data formats, schema, communication protocols at the design and development phases.

Figure 3 shows how SMARTY needs to also integrate workload placement, orchestration and integration with existing technologies (i.e. IPsec, MACsec, TLS) through middleware in order to optimally optimize the resources and drive the data planes (i.e. in the formation of SDP isles of trust), the establishment of PQC links, the utilization of CC trusted execution environments and so forth.

B. Dedicated Accelerators

SMARTY will provide a test implementation of a QR secured-IC, to be used as an isolated Hardware Security Module (HSM); e.g., attached to an edge device for secure crypto execution, key generation and storage. Following the latest NIST candidates to be standardized, CRYSTALS-

Fig. 3. Overall view at high level of SMARTY: orchestration of results.

Kyber will be the primary choice for key-establishment and CRYSTALS-Dilithium for digital signatures. We will follow a tight hardware and software (firmware) co-design process, including the inclusion of specialized hardware accelerators to enable the execution of the chosen PQC algorithms within the typical memory and speed constraints of small, embedded devices. Furthermore, the QR-SE will be designed with crypto-agility in mind and hybrid cryptographic support (i.e., classical RSA/ECC-based cryptography will still be supported) to enable a smooth transition to PQC.

PQC accelerators can be integrated tightly or loosely coupled with the processor pipeline. While the former could provide higher efficiency, it is generally less flexible and portable. Hence, we opt for a Loosely Coupled Accelerator (LCA). LCAs are particularly convenient to perform coarse-grain computations, as it is the case of data encryption and decryption performed by the PQC accelerator. This implies that the PQC accelerator must have some local storage, and some direct interface with the memory hierarchy, either a cache memory or DRAM. To manage the interactions between the local and external PQC accelerator memories, we build on the use of a DMA controller, which provides decoupling between data transfers and computation. We will provide appropriate device drivers for Linux to interface the PQC accelerator. In particular, the PQC accelerator will be a memory mapped device in the user space so that it can be properly interfaced. The PQC accelerator will be integrated as a combination of hardware and software modules with the aim of maximizing efficiency without sacrificing performance, and ease reuse across different PQC algorithms. In particular, the PQC accelerator already realizes at hardware level the most compute intensive and time-consuming functions such as: (i) Key generation (KeyGen) acceleration by means of a Gaussian systemizer, (ii) Encapsulation acceleration by means of a syndrome encoder and (iii) Decapsulation acceleration by means of a syndrome decoder.

C. Continuous Trustworthy Semantic Integration

SMARTY will provide a concept and implementation for Continuous Semantic Integration (CSI). A swarm of SMARTY

devices (things) continuously change, e.g., appear and disappear from the environment, upgrade their capabilities, need to integrate, and communicate with brownfield devices etc. Things that interoperate are diverse regarding their capabilities (what they can do), resources (what they can run on), connectivity (what protocol they use to communicate) and they would need dynamic decision-making. Apps, running on them, have certain requirements for devices too. Apart from devices, apps may run elsewhere in Edge or Cloud. This extremely dynamic behavior is the reason why we need semantic integration, and in particular why we need Continuous Semantic Integration. CSI is the backbone between devices, as represented via Standardized Semantic Interfaces, and Swarm Intelligence Apps that are created and run based on CSI. SMARTY aims to establish a seamless integration of heterogeneous devices providing standardized semantic interfaces that enable data access from the Edge. Such standardised semantic interfaces will cover aspects such as hardware capabilities, software features including data descriptions and functions preconditions and effects. Standardised Semantic Interfaces will allow SMARTY to manage complexity at various levels (device, Edge, Cloud), and will allow the management of available AI models running on disparate devices. This integration is applicable to both newly developed IoT devices and existing brownfield devices. We aim to develop a methodology to create reference data models (potentially including established data models, such as ROS-based standards, including Unified Robot Description Format (urdf) and OMG Data distribution Service (DDS) for Smart Factories) and to create mappings integrating brownfield data models into such reference semantic information models. Mappings will use a declarative and reusable approach and will cover both streaming and static data.

D. Programmability of Data Plane Accelerators

In the data plane, the 6G data plane programmability shall undergo expansion via the use of a unified programming language for both specific in-network functions and the speedy AI at switches, advanced smart NICs, and edge containers. Novel switch platforms enabled by P4 technology have emerged, combining programmable ASIC resources with ASIC+FPGA resources, and DPU having specific hardware accelerators and local CPU/GPU functionalities. The data plane will allocate and instantiate security network functions to implement extreme acceleration of networking and in-network functions in the programmable ASIC, and a combination of programmable AI models running in local GPU/CPU, with minimum delay budget. Based on its threat model, security policies, and hardware capabilities, certain applications and security measures shall trigger AI on a per-packet, per-train, or time-window level. DPUs shall be incorporated into specific SDN edge devices, such as an IoT gateway or an edge node interface, or a data center gateway.

Several recent attempts have been made to deploy AI in programmable bare metal switches, but current arithmetic unit support is limited due to vendors targeting hardware acceleration of specific network functions like address match,

Fig. 4. Software Defined Perimeters working together with Confidential Computing.

hash, checksums, and limited packet metadata structures. The next-generation switch platforms are expected to support local FPGA/GPU availability with programmable pipeline interconnectivity. Moreover, specific distillation studies will allow to map the behavior of an AI engine into such pipeline structures, having the AI structure defined as a bulk of flow entries. This will enable AI models to run at the switch at wire speed and will allow to dynamically change the AI structure in few milliseconds.

Smart NICs offer similar programmability levels, combined with the possibility of local computation, hardware acceleration, and functional modules provided as a software development kit and libraries (such as NVIDIA DOCA), including P4 support. In cases where AI is not directly implementable in data plane devices, an accelerated channel shall be designed to get the AI module as close as possible to the device in terms of resource awareness and delay. For instance, the latest DPU technologies may rely on specific bypass communication channels that exploit real-time analytics (such as RDMA and GPUDirect RDMA) between the DPU ASIC and the internal resources of the co-located server, utilizing the large bandwidth capabilities provided by the PCI Express Gen. 5 bus.

E. Software Defined Perimeters

Figure 4 shows the concept of Software Defined Perimeters in SMARTY. Cloud or edge platforms with heterogeneous processors, systems and subsystems that may also support confidential computing, are clustered through software premises, isolating them from the rest of the heterogeneous fabric and working collaboratively.

The following topics will be then investigated in relation to SDP:

- Security Analysis: Investigating the security properties of SDP and evaluating its effectiveness in protecting against cyber-attacks.
- Performance Evaluation: Evaluating the performance of SDP in terms of latency, throughput, and scalability, especially in AI-intensive edge computing platforms large-scale networks.

- Identity and Access Management: Researching identity and access management in SDP environments and developing solutions for secure authentication, authorization, and accounting.
- Interoperability: Investigating interoperability challenges between SDP and other security technologies, such as firewalls, intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDPS), and virtual private networks (VPNs).

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper has discussed current research challenges to make trustworthy Edge AI a reality and presented the overall vision of the SMARTY project covering both its vision and research agenda. Over the next three years SMARTY will develop key technologies and components that are needed to make trustworthy Edge AI a reality. SMARTY will contribute to position Europe as a leader in hardware and software components for Edge AI improving its competitiveness in the global arena.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This paper was partly funded by the European Commission through the Chips Act Joint Undertaking project SMARTY (Grant no. 101140087).

REFERENCES

- [1] S. B. Calo, M. Touna, D. C. Verma, and A. Cullen, "Edge computing architecture for applying AI to IoT," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*, 2017, pp. 3012–3016.
- [2] A. Y. Ding, M. Janssen, and J. Crowcroft, "Trustworthy and sustainable edge ai: A research agenda," in *2021 Third IEEE International Conference on Trust, Privacy and Security in Intelligent Systems and Applications (TPS-ISA)*, 2021, pp. 164–172.
- [3] Z. Liu, K.-K. R. Choo, and J. Grossschadl, "Securing edge devices in the post-quantum internet of things using lattice-based cryptography," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 158–162, 2018.
- [4] A. Moubayed, A. Refaey, and A. Shami, "Software-defined perimeter (sdp): State of the art secure solution for modern networks," *IEEE Network*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 226–233, 2019.
- [5] Z. Ni, A. Khalid, and M. O'Neill, "High performance fpga-based post quantum cryptography implementations," in *2022 32nd International Conference on Field-Programmable Logic and Applications (FPL)*, 2022, pp. 456–457.
- [6] K. Chen, "Confidential high-performance computing in the public cloud," *IEEE Internet Computing*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 24–32, 2023.